

"THE LAWS OF MEDICINE" IS THE BASIS OF MEDICINE AND PHYSIOLOGY

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Abstract. The article discusses the importance of the works and teachings of Abu Ali ibn Sino, who, along with the great encyclopedic scholars of the Eastern Renaissance. It is said that Abu Ali ibn Sino reached a high level in the science of medicine in his time and is even recognized today, which is of great practical importance, especially in these difficult days.

Keywords: medicine, biology, Renaissance, Central Asia, Laws of Medicine, Avicenna.

Our great ancestors, such as Abu Ali ibn Sina, Ahmad al-Farghani Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Mahmud Kashgari, in addition to being extremely talented, achieved the status of teachers to the whole world in their sciences. This period determined the principles of the rise of world development. In addition, we would like to dwell on the contributions of Abu Ali ibn Sina to medical science. Introducing the future generation to the contributions of the sultan of medical science, Abu Ali ibn Sina, to enlightenment, culture and the development of medicine is one of the tasks facing us, natural scientists. The sultan of medical science, one of our great thinkers who brought the culture of the peoples of Central Asia to the forefront of world culture, is Abu Ali ibn Sina [1].

Abu Ali ibn Sina's systematization of medical and pharmaceutical knowledge, new methods of diagnosis and treatment, and analysis of the possibilities of transmutation of minerals are some of the great ideas he implemented in the natural sciences. Abu Ali ibn Sina's works "Canons of Medicine" and "Guide for Travelers" (Fiy tadbir al musafiriyyin) have served as indispensable guides for medical specialists and the people of the world in general for several centuries and to this day [2].

We are witnessing once again, especially in these trying times, that Abu Ali ibn Sina achieved a high level in medical science in his time and is still receiving special recognition today. After all, today the information of all medical organizations in the world on how people should behave during a pandemic confirms how correct the scientific legacy left by our great physician a thousand years ago is. The contributions of our great grandfather to the development of medical science are enormous. The world-famous and famous "Canons of Medicine" are worthy of admiration. This book consists of five volumes:

Volume 1: Medical science - a description of acute and chronic diseases, their diagnosis, treatment, surgery.

Volume 2: Stories about natural herbal medicines

Volumes 3 and 4: recommendations for the treatment of diseases in the human body, fractures in the limbs.

Volume 5: Description of the properties of complex drugs independently prepared by Ibn Sina and the use of the writings of ancient physicians in Europe and Asia as a source. In addition, our grandfather's works on ethics, which serve humanity today, are worthy of praise [3].

In his works on ethics, Ibn Sina taught that people should pay special attention to such moral rules as humility, honor, courage, honesty, and sincerity in their daily lives, and these qualities, which are the basis of education, are extremely valuable in our country's general education today. In particular, Ibn Sina noted the need to educate and raise children in school, and said that all people's children should be attracted to school and educated and raised together, and opposed the education of children alone at home.

References

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